

RESEARCH ARTICLE ↓

Entrepreneurship Education and Performance of SMEs in Enugu State

Authors

Nkechi Anthonia, Idoko¹, Ugochukwu, Loveth Ngozi PhD², & Ugwu, Fidelis³

Authors	Affiliation
1 st	Department of Library and Information Science, Enugu State Polytechnic, Iwollo
2 nd & 3 rd	Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Abstract

The study evaluated the entrepreneurship education and performance of SMEs in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between training workshops and competences development and evaluate the relationship between professional support network and productivity of SMEs. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of three thousand, seven hundred and forty-five (3745) staff was used. The adequate sample size of 345, using Freund and William’s statistic formula. Two hundred and fifty-eight (258) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analysed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Person correlation (r) test. The findings indicated training workshops had positive significant relationship with continues development of SMEs in Enugu as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n = 258) = .379 < 757, p < .05$ and professional support network had positive significant relationship with productivity of SMEs as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n = 258) = .401 < 975, p < .05$. The study concluded that training workshops and professional support network had positive significant relationship with competences development and productivity of SMEs. The study recommended among others that Entrepreneurship tutors, teachers, lecturers or trainers should also be trained in other to ensure their competence in impacting the knowledge to others. Also, they should ensure that students practice the theoretical aspect of what has been taught if the need arises.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education; Performance of SMEs; Enugu State

Introduction

Unemployment is a recurrent dilemma in Nigeria due to limited resources. However, it should be clearly understood that no government of any nation would be able to wipe out unemployment, since there are limited resources. The current economic trends and government policies call for diversification from dependence on oil (Kulo, Agbogo and Okudare, 2017). Entrepreneurship is a key driver of economy; wealth and a high majority of jobs are created by small businesses started by entrepreneurial minded individuals, many of whom go on to create businesses. It is the belief of many experience business people, political leaders, economists and educators that fostering a robust entrepreneurial culture will maximize individual and collective economic and a success on a local, national, and global scale. It is with this belief that the educational sectors deem it fit to inculcate entrepreneurship education in academic curriculum. Entrepreneurial education is expected to prepare learners to be creative and productive citizens and nation builders. Hasan, Khan and Nabi (2017), entrepreneurship education is essential to achieve successful socioeconomic development and sustainable development because entrepreneurship is a combination of actions and, indeed, entrepreneurship education is vital for socioeconomic landscape, as it could play an influential role in equipping and changing one's attitude to becoming an entrepreneur.

Small and medium enterprises are major players in the competition and growth of economies. The 21st-century skills as part of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) are vital, and entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial thinking are now crucial than ever. That is why entrepreneurship education and enterprise education must have an even stronger place in every type of education, from primary school to higher education. It is an important way for entrepreneurs to acquire resources, enhance innovative ability and innovative personality, and build multi-level learning channels for entrepreneurs by integrating various knowledge and value systems (Wei, Liu and Sha, 2019). From knowledge learning to skills improvement, entrepreneurship education includes general ability development and improvement of professional ability. business performance becomes an important aspect for an organization to manage well, for that reason constitutes an integral part of all activities and operations performed by entrepreneurs to strengthen their business (Mahmood, et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurship is no doubt a dynamic process of vision, change, and creation. It requires an application of energy and passion towards the creation and implementation of new ideas and creative solutions. Entrepreneurship education is designed to develop entrepreneurial attitudes for future entrepreneurs. It stimulates young people to think about entrepreneurship and the role of the business community in economic and social development. A strong need to build something and to feel that what was build is due to personal efforts is a primary motivation. Therefore, by combing new and existing resources with innovative ideas, entrepreneurs add value through the commercialization of new products, the creation of new jobs and the building of new firms (Emezue and Onwujekwe, 2020). With entrepreneurial education, entrepreneurship is gradually gaining a permanent position in education. Next, for the future, it is important to join forces and coordinate activities. So that the national education system and entrepreneurship policies are further strengthened. However, the most important goal is that through education and training the entrepreneurs of tomorrow stand up. This has led to the study on entrepreneurship education and performance of SMEs in Enugu state

Statement of Problem

SMEs are estimated to be more than 95%, offering over 60% of the employment opportunities in the private sector. The concept of lifelong learning is essential to the competitiveness of the knowledge economy. It applies to all levels of education and training and concerns all stages of life as well as the different forms of apprenticeship. Small and medium businesses account for the transition to a market economy playing an important part in innovation, income generation and dynamism in economy and employment. Entrepreneurship education is very important as a catalyst for development focus, in line with the entrepreneurial culture of a nation.

Entrepreneurship is a process that leads to creation of SMEs while performance is a prominent achievement of SMEs. It defines how SMEs reach a final conclusion to accomplish a goal. There are a number of problems limiting the growth of small and medium size businesses. Most of these problems are as a result of lack of involvement of entrepreneurs in the field of entrepreneurship due to lack of training workshops and professional support network. The root of the matter is that entrepreneurship education is loaded with worries or challenges in most developing countries. The challenges become a stumbling block in their desire to be among the top economies in the world.

Entrepreneurship education is concerned with fostering creative skills that can be applied in practices, education, and environments supporting innovation. However, if the problems of entrepreneurship is not been solved, there is high tendency that students graduates in entrepreneurship courses would be half baked due to incompetence development which will lead to low productivity when involved in the activities of SMEs. This shows that entrepreneurship education is capable of bringing about the desired socioeconomic and political changes in the country. As such, entrepreneurship education should not only be inculcated in the academic curriculum of student just as a name but schools ensure that its activities is carried out both theoretically and practically. Hence, the study of entrepreneurship education and performance of SMEs in Enugu state.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study evaluates entrepreneurship education and performance of SMEs in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between training workshops and competences development of SMEs in Enugu
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between professional support network and productivity of SMEs

Research Questions

The following research question guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between Training workshops and continues development of SMEs in Enugu?
- ii. What is the relationship between professional support network and productivity of SMEs?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Training workshops has relationship with continues development of SMEs in Enugu.
- ii. Professional support network has relationship with productivity of SMEs.

Significance of the Study

The study will be favourable in highlighting the importance of entrepreneurship education and its importance in enhancing the performance of SMEs. It will also to inculcate the zeal to be innovative to students and the importance of skills which will help them to be self-reliant even while in school and after school.

Conceptual Review

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a topic that fascinates the brightest and wealthiest people. There is something magical about how a talented entrepreneur can change the world. But who are entrepreneurs? What makes them special? What is the definition of an entrepreneur? In this article, we will look at the five major elements of an entrepreneur. The presented elements will serve as a checklist to determine whether you qualify as an entrepreneur. Remember that even if you pass the first hurdle and are considered an entrepreneur, you will still need to play your cards right to be in the elite group of “successful entrepreneurs” (Criniti, 2021; Ukwuani, Mbah & Ugochukwu, 2018). An entrepreneurial mindset is an attitude that relegates different values to assets and openings than the rest of the crowd. It is basically the ability to turn problems into opportunities. A particular arrangement of convictions, information and perspectives that drives pioneering conduct, an outlook that encourages inventiveness and advancement, changing the game and being exceptional (Vaishali, 2021).

Education

Education is fundamental to development and growth. The human mind makes possible all development achievements, from health advances and agricultural innovations to efficient public administration and private sector growth. For countries to reap these benefits fully, they need to unleash the potential of the human mind. And there is no better tool for doing so than education (King, 2011). Education is a purposeful activity directed at achieving certain aims, such as transmitting knowledge or fostering skills and character traits. These aims may include the development of understanding, rationality, kindness, and honesty. Today, educational goals increasingly

encompass new ideas such as the liberation of learners, skills needed for modern society, empathy, and complex vocational skills.

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education is seen as the process of creating something different with value by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the accompanying financial, psychological, and social risk, and receiving the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction (Hisrich, Peters and Shepherd, 2017). Entrepreneurship education is viewed as an attempt to create value through recognition of business opportunities, communicative, and management skills to mobilize human, financial and material resources necessary to bring a project to function (Koa and Stevenson, 2020). The entrepreneurship education is a relatively new phenomenon in Nigerian higher education institutions. This occur when the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) adopted small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) as the building block of the country's economy and the right entrepreneurs to realize the objective of setting up small and medium scale enterprises were not available despite the existence of millions of unemployed youths, including higher institution graduates who regrettably, do not have the requisite skills and experiences for entrepreneurship in the country (Nwekeaku, 2013).

Training Workshops

Training is the action of informing or instructing your employees on a certain task in order to help them improve their performance or knowledge. If people are to perform their job to the highest possible standard, they must be effectively and efficiently trained, (Mango, 2023; Mbah, Aga, & Onyia,2018). A workshop is a long interactive meeting or educational session designed to create a specialized result. Workshops are longer than the typical business meeting and require more preparation beforehand. Workshops typically involve a central trainer or facilitator who works with a set of sponsors to design the sequence of presentations, plan collaborative activities, and ensure the workshop will lead to the desired result. Workshops emphasize hands-on interaction (Lucid, 2023).

Professional Support Network

Professional networking is an important part of a successful career, where you connect with others in your industry. Networking can help you learn new skills, discover opportunities and build valuable relationships. Learning more about networking can lead you to career success, (Indeed Editorial Team, 2022). Networking is one of the most important skills for entrepreneurs and is one which you have the opportunity to practice on programs. Networking involves building and maintaining contacts and relationships with other people. The personal networks which you accumulate over time, both socially and professionally can be an invaluable resource (Cambridge, 2023). Networking and professional support are advanced and not gender-specific, studies show that there is of more benefit in this area. This fact makes it more urgent that people increase their efforts to form a support network (Victoria, 2018).

Performance

Performance is defined as the accomplishment of a given task measured against present known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed. In a contract, performance is deemed to be the fulfilment of an obligation, in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract (McNamara, 2018; Eze, Agbo, & Mbah 2022). It is the completion of a task with application of knowledge, skills and abilities. Performance involves analysing an organizations performance against its objectives and goals. In other words, organizational performance comprises real results or outputs compared with intended outputs. Performance is a relation between cost (operation cost the organization) and the value of benefits obtained (Cosmin, Gheorghe and Raluca, 2012; Ede, & Mbah, 2020).

Competences Development

Developing competencies is about learning and practicing specific competencies. Some of them we already have because of our traits, values, and ethics. But others require a more formal development process, such as pursuing an academic degree. Then, in a work environment, competence development is the process of growing competencies through training. And training can be either formal or informal (Zavvy, 2023). Developing competence is identifying the skills, talents, characteristics and knowledge you require to perform your job effectively and training or practising to improve them. Taking time to enhance competence helps you improve your job performance, allowing you to advance your career (Indeed, 2023).

Productivity

Profitability is the primary goal of all business ventures. Without profitability the business will not survive in the long run. So, measuring current and past profitability and projecting future profitability is very important. Profitability is measured with income and expenses. Income is money generated from the activities of the business (Johanns, 2021). Profit is an absolute number determined by the amount of income or revenue above and beyond the costs or expenses a company incurs. Profitability is a measurement of efficiency – and ultimately its success or failure. It is a business's ability to produce a return on an investment based on its resources in comparison with an alternative investment (Potters, 2021).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source: Researcher, 2023

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the social cognitive theory by Albert Bandura in the year 1986 and the modern growth model by Solow in the year 1957. Social learning network provides multi-level learning channels for student entrepreneurs to continuously improve their skills in learning and practice.

Social Cognitive Theory

This theory was developed by Albert Bandura 1986. Social cognitive theory conceives individuals as agents and active contributors to the development of the circumstances that surround their lives (Bandura, 2018). Individuals are tended to pursue their goals if they consider their own abilities and actions are capable of achieving the desired results (Bandura, et al., 2003). Entrepreneurship education helps improve their cognition, constantly adjust their thoughts and actions, and make their entrepreneurship more directional, coherent and meaningful. This study employs the theory of social cognition to examine how learners in entrepreneurship education can enhance their ability to identify opportunities through political skills, which in turn affects entrepreneurs' innovative awareness, innovative ability, and innovative personality. Learning from observation to participation (Tavella and Franco, 2015), in a network (Chen and Chang, 2014), learning is no longer a single behaviour but is implemented in a complex system of relationships. Individuals can transcend immediate circumstances, through self-guidance, shape the present toward the realization of outcomes and goals (Bandura, 2018). General education focuses on the overall development of students, and the entrepreneurial curriculum system lays the foundation for the overall improvement of students' entrepreneurial ability. From observation to participation, the social learning network provides multi-level learning channels for student entrepreneurs to continuously improve their skills in learning and practice. Therefore, entrepreneurship education might enhance the confidence of the students that he will be able to solve new and unexpected problems.

Modern Growth Model

Solow (1957) developed a growth model capable of distinguishing between shifts in the aggregate production function due to technical change and movements along the curve due to increases in capital stock. Solow calculated that one eighth of US income growth was attributable to increases in capital, with the remainder—the vast majority—“attributable to technical change.” However, this Solow residual contains more than technical change: changes in human capital, institutions, lending, and entrepreneurship, are contained within the residual. Later papers remedied these deficiencies by building on Solow's framework, which has remained a workhorse for generations.

Arrow (1962) incorporated human capital via learning by - doing process. His model embedded the stock of knowledge within a heterogeneous, time - indexed capital stock, so that a unit of capital created in a given time period produces more output than capital produced in previous periods. Because increases in knowledge are manifested in more productive capital, capital investment in the current period also increases the stock of knowledge. This increase in knowledge makes capital produced in later periods more productive than it would otherwise be. Because of this external effect, the benefits of investment are not fully captured by investors —leading to an inefficiently low level of investment. While the model assumes homogeneous labour, Arrow comments that “the [exogenous] growth rate of the labour force incorporates qualitative as well as quantitative increase.” Left untouched is the potential for endogenous “qualitative increases” based on agents’ choice of non-productive human capital investment in place of labourer leisure

Empirical Review

The Relationship between Training Workshops and Competences Development of SMEs in Enugu

Elnaga and Imran (2013) conducted a study on the Effect of Training on Employee Performance. Employee is a blood stream of any business. The accomplishment or disaster of the firm depends on its employee performance. Hence, top management realized the importance of investing in training and development for the sake of improving employee performance. This conceptual paper aimed at studying the effect of training on employee performance and to provide suggestion as to how firm can improve its employee performance through effective training programs. The research approach adopted for the study conforms to qualitative research, as it reviews the literature and multiple case studies on the importance of training in enhancing the performance of the workforce. Further the paper goes on to analyse and understand the theoretical framework and models related to employee development through training and development programs, and its effect on employee performance and on the basis of the review of the current evidence of such a relationship, offers suggestions for the top management in form of a checklist, appropriate for all businesses, to assess the employee performance and to find out the true cause(s) of the performance problem so the problem could be solved in time through desired training program. The study in hand faces the limitations as there are no adequate indications to correlate directly the relationship between training and employee performance. Hence, there is a need for conducting empirical research in future to test the proposition discussed in the study. The study in hand provides brief overview of the literature about training effectiveness and how it contributes in enhancing the employee performance.

Omolo (2015) carried out a study on Training and Development on Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kisumu County, Kenya. The increasing interest in training and development is due to the assumption that employees and the way they are managed are critical to the success of a firm. The increasing pressures from the rapid changes occurring in the business environment have led to a variety of responses among organizations. Training and development is therefore emerging as a proactive way of reducing such pressures. This study intends to investigate the influence of training and development on the performance of SMEs in Kisumu County. SMEs are emerging as a reliable alternative to poverty alleviation. This sector remains a major revenue earner to the government and a source of employment to many people. However, SMEs in Kenya and in Kisumu County in particular, face peculiar challenges that affect their performance and limit their capacity to contribute effectively to sustainable development. They lack effective performance standards, Training and development that do not support appropriately skilled personnel. The study investigated the influence of training and development, on employee performance in SMEs in Kisumu. The ecological theory of small business growth and development was used to guide the study. The study was conducted in SMEs in Kisumu County using cross sectional survey research design, on a target population of 777 and a sample of 260 clustered randomly selected SMEs, which represent 30% of the target population. Data was collected using structured, semi structured, Likert scale questionnaire and focus group discussion techniques. Data was analysed using percentages and multiple regression techniques, reported using tables, charts, graphs and figures. The finding of the study showed that the performance of an SME is associated with the status of training and development and that the better the status of training and development in an SME, the higher the performance of the SME.

Habiyaremye, Ayebale and Wanyama (2017) conducted a study on a Job-Rotation, Utilization of Workshops, and Performance of SMEs: An Empirical Study from the Gasabo District in Rwanda. This study addresses an important aspect of building small- and medium-sized enterprises’ (SME) performance capacity through human resource

development. It specifically studies the experiences of manufacturing SMEs in Rwanda to demonstrate the performance implications of using workshops and job-rotation in small entrepreneurial firms. Given its unique commitment in the region for building necessary support for developing enterprises, Rwanda was a particularly interesting context to study this aspect. Our study included 101 firms drawn from Gasabo, a district in capital Kigali. With the help of a regression analysis, we found support for a positive direct link between job-rotation and SME performance. We, however, did not find a similar result regarding workshops and SME performance. In order to examine the effects of job-rotation and workshops in more depth, we tested for the combined effect of these two practices. Our findings demonstrate the value of workshops when combined with job-rotation among SMEs in our study setting. With these findings, our study demonstrates how local firms and advocates of workshops can effectively use this method to enhance SME performance.

Okonkwo, Onyeze and Ochiaka (2019) conducted a study on the Empowering the Uneducated Youths in Nigeria through Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria. The general aim of this research work is to examine “the ways of empowering the uneducated youths in Nigeria through Small and Medium Scale Enterprise: A Study of Ezeagu Local Government Area, Enugu State”. The specific objectives of this research work include the following: to identify the number of SME formed by uneducated youths in Ezeagu LGA, to examine the roles of small and medium scale enterprises in youth empowerment in Enugu State. For a successful completion of this research work, the researcher made use of both primary and secondary methods of data collection for information gathering. The population of the study was 1308 while the sample size of 306 was gotten through Taro Yamene formula. The data collected were presented in tables and analysed with simple percentage while the hypotheses stated were tested with chi square. The findings made includes: the roles of small and medium scale enterprises in youth empowerment in Enugu State are entrepreneurship promotion, provision of employment opportunities, mobilization of savings and financial resources for productive enterprise activities and equitable growth across regions and between men and women, the contributions of government in SME development are provision of infrastructural development, promotion of small and medium scale enterprises through its policies, provision of capital and loans to small and medium scale business owners and provision of skill acquisition centers in diverse areas. In conclusion, capital formation has affected the role of small and medium scale enterprises in youth empowerment in Enugu State to a very great extent, the challenges militating against the efforts of small and medium scale enterprises in youth empowerment in Enugu State are financial problems, management problems, infrastructure problems and socio-cultural problems.

Oluka, and Nwafor, (2022) carried out a study on the Entrepreneurial Competencies: A Sine Quanon for Successful Operation of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) by Graduates of Technology and Vocational Education from Tertiary Institutions in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study investigated the entrepreneurial competencies needed by Technology and Vocational Education (TVE) graduates for effective operation of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Enugu state. Three research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population for the study was 3,306 respondents comprising 113 TVE lecturers in tertiary institutions and 3,193 registered managers of small and medium scale enterprises in Enugu state. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 41 TVE lecturers and 302 SMEs managers getting a total of 343 respondents. A structured questionnaire containing 25 items was validated by three experts, two from TVE Department and one. The 25 items in the Questionnaire were retained after validation, and was used for data collection of the study. Test-retest method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument and data collected was analysed with Pearson product moment correlation which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.78. A total of 332 copies out of 343 copies of the questionnaire were correctly filled and returned, and were used for the study, representing 96.8 percent return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that TVE graduates of tertiary institutions in Enugu state require managerial, communication and marketing competencies for effective operation of SMEs.

Okoli and Agugwu (2022) carried out a study on Uncovering the Relationship between Entrepreneurship Training on Business Growth among SMEs in Southeast Nigeria. The growth of any business is a major concern that is determined by different factors. Entrepreneurship training has been identified as one that can play a key role in the growth of SMEs around the world. The objective of this study was to examine the relationship between entrepreneurship training and business growth among SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria. A survey procedure was accepted for the study and the study was based on both secondary and primary data. The total population of this study is two hundred and fifty

(250) small businesses (SMEs). Data were collected using questionnaire and analysed using Ordinary Least Square Regression. This study revealed that entrepreneurship training has a positive impact on the business growth of the SMEs in Southeast Nigeria. The study concluded that entrepreneurship training is one of the key factors influencing SME growth, as well as the extent to which further training is based on the availability and relevance of training needs and programs.

Barinua and Okoro (2022) carried out a study on Entrepreneurial Characteristics and Business Performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in Enugu State. The main objective of this study is to determine the relationship between the dimensions of entrepreneurial characteristics and measures of business performance in small and medium enterprises in Enugu State. Based on the review of journals, textbooks, magazines and online materials, the findings revealed that risk has a significant positive relationship with measures of business performance (Profitability, market share and customer satisfaction). Secondly, the findings revealed that competitive aggressiveness has a significant positive relationship with measures of business performance (Profitability, market share and customer satisfaction). Lastly, the findings also revealed that Competence has a significant positive relationship with measures of business performance (Profitability, market share and customer satisfaction). Therefore, the study concluded that risk taking enhances measures of business performance (profitability, market share and customer satisfaction). Also, competitive aggressiveness enhances measures of business performance (profitability, market share and customer satisfaction). Furthermore, Leadership Competence enhances measures of business performance (profitability, market share and customer satisfaction). Hence the study recommended that entrepreneurial leaders should take good calculated risks, become competitive aggressive and possess the required competence as a means of improving the business performance through increase in profitability, market share and customer satisfaction.

The Relationship between Professional Support Network and Productivity of SMEs

Mario, Haase and Pereira (2016) carried out a study on Empirical Study about the Role of Social Networks in SME Performance. This study shows the role of social networks in the performance of small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in an inland region of Portugal. The main objective is to ascertain the reasons for adhering to social networks and to understand if this type of network influences performance in this firm sector. Design/methodology/approach: To fulfil these aims, quantitative research was adopted, based on application of a questionnaire. The final sample is formed of 86 SMEs. Findings: Based on the results obtained, it is concluded that the SMEs studied are connected to social networks, especially Facebook. The principal reason for this type of firm connecting to social networks has to do with the possibility of presenting services to a greater number of potential customers. Practical implications: The empirical evidence obtained shows that the reasons associated with cost reduction influence both financial indicators (profit growth) and non-financial indicators (human resource results). Again, communication and innovation influence only non-financial performance (level of satisfaction). Originality/value: This study contributes to advancing theory in the field of social networks in SMEs. More precisely, it suggests that to assess their performance, SME leaders should not use only measures of a financial nature (sales volume, level of growth, etc.), but rather in combination with non-financial indicators such as customer satisfaction, reputation and others.

Egele, Muhammad and Mutenyo (2018) conducted a study on the Entrepreneurial personal networks and performance of small and medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Kano State, Nigeria. This study evaluated the effect of entrepreneurial personal networks on performance of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs), using 393 respondents selected from manufacturing, education, trade and other services in Kano state, Nigeria. SMEs' efforts toward providing solution to the problem of unemployment in Nigeria and the world at large face stiff opposition from their conception as a result of many factors being responsible. The study employed cross sectional research design in which data was collected using mixed strategies, interview and questionnaire, results using Pearson linear correlation and regression analysis. Results indicate there is positive and significant relationship between SMEs performance and entrepreneurial personal networks. Entrepreneurial personal networks had a significant effect on SMEs performance. The study adds value to the growing body of knowledge in the field of entrepreneurial development activities.

Fatai, et al. (2018) conducted a study on the Nexus Between Informal Networks and Risk-Taking: Implications for Improving the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. An evolving dimension of entrepreneurial research reveals that entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial networks are critical factors in fostering performance outcomes. However, there is dearth of studies that examined the relationship between risk-

taking dimension of entrepreneurial orientation and informal networks on SMEs performance. This study set out to examine the influence of risk-taking and informal networks on the performance of selected small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. Descriptive research design in which questionnaire was used to collect data from 381 SMEs owner-managers guided the study. Correlation, multiple regression and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) were employed to test the hypotheses with Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) for measurement model validation. The results revealed that both risk-taking and informal networks have significant positive effect on SMEs performance.

Aladejebi, (2020) conducted a study on the Impact of Entrepreneurial Networks on The Performance of Small business in Nigeria. Networking is ultimately the process of exchanging information between two or more people; in this case, entrepreneurs. The main objective of this paper is to look into the firm attributes related to formal networking and investigate whether membership in formal networks in the form of business associations and industry/trade-specific associations has been an impact on the growth of SMEs business in Lagos, Nigeria. A purposeful sample was used to select respondents. Questionnaires designed to examine the views of the entrepreneur about SME networking were distributed among two SME groups, namely Nigerian Association of Small Scale Industrialists (NASSI), Lagos, and PHARMALLIANCE (Association of Community Pharmacists). The research instrument was based on a five-point Likert scale. The questionnaire administered contained 2 parts, Part 1: contains general information, while Part 2: contains specific questions relating to networking. The results of the analysis showed a generally positive overview of SME networking in Nigeria. The respondents mostly agree across both groups that networking is of great benefit to their businesses.

Alkahtani, Nordin and Rizwan (2020) carried out a study on Government support enhance the relation between networking structure and sustainable competitive performance among SMEs. The underlining study's main objective is to examine how networking structure (density and centrality) affects sustainable competitive performance in Pakistan's SMEs. Hence, small enterprises a significant source of economic development, employment, and value creation. Therefore, on the base of previous literature, we developed hypothesis related government financial support and network structure, and data collected through structured questionnaires from top management of SMEs. Findings The results indicate that density has a positive and significant effect on sustainable competitive performance, while centrality has an insignificant impact on SCP. Furthermore, government financial support strongly and significantly supports the relation between networking structure and SCP in Pakistan. Practical implications This research has several recommendations for the government to adequately support small enterprises because owners have a networking system at the local and international level but have a lack of environment. Originality/value Government plays a crucial role in small- and medium-sized enterprises boost performance and economic growth because it creates employment opportunities, poverty reduction, and economic development. Nevertheless, from the last decades, due to some organizational policies and environmental flexibility, SMEs face a lot of challenges which became a barrier such as lack of government subsidies, incentives, and taxes in emerging economies. To bridge the above challenges of SMEs, the current study is conducted because before this there was no such literature who underline the current challenges in emerging economies.

Zahid, et al. (2021) carried out a study on an Investigation of Entrepreneurial SMEs' Network Capability and Social Capital to Accomplish Innovativeness: A Dynamic Capability Perspective. The empirical assessment of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) from different perspectives is an ever-green research agenda because of their enormous contributions to developed and developing economies. However, the size and resource limitations hinder the progress of SMEs. In this regard, business networks and connections have great potential to enable SMEs' access to scarce and valuable resources. Entrepreneurial SMEs' healthy relationships and connections with stakeholders can yield dynamism and innovativeness. Despite that, the understanding of these networks and connections over the innovation capability of entrepreneurial SMEs is limited and needs further empirical investigation. Thus, this study is among the preliminary ones which assay the impact of network capability on innovation capability in the entrepreneurial SMEs context. This study also investigates the above relationship through social capital. The study ground its assumptions based on dynamic capability theory and collected feedback via a questionnaire from 199 entrepreneurial SMEs operating in Pakistan. After ensuring the reliability and validity of collected feedback, the study employed the partial least square structural equation modelling technique to analyse it. Results of the study expand the understanding by unveiling that network capability has a substantial positive impact on innovation capability. This implies that by fortifying network capability, entrepreneurial SMEs substantially enhance their capabilities to innovate. Results also affirm that by building strong network capability, entrepreneurial SMEs boost their social

capital, which subsequently has a positive and significant impact on innovation capability. Finally, by operationalizing the proposed model in the entrepreneurial SMEs context, this study made novel contributions to the literature of network capability, social capital, innovation capability, and entrepreneurship.

Methodology

The area of the study comprised of Seven (7) small and medium enterprises selected within Enugu metropolis, Enugu state, Nigeria. They are: Agro Prospero Nigeria Limited, 194, Abakaliki Road, Emene; Alfrecon Nigeria Limited, 29, Owkuzu street, Uwani, Enugu; Crystal Chemical Ltd, Abakaliki-Enugu Expressway, Juhel Nig. Ltd, Nkwubor Road Emene., Sunchi Integrated Farms Ltd., Emene Ind. Layout, Allsons Industries Limited, 55, Akpo Street, Achara Layout, Enugu and Aqua Rapha Investment Ltd, 9th mile. These organizations were chosen because of entrepreneurship education skills involved in their activities and with capital base of not less than 10million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of three thousand, seven hundred and forty-five (3745) staff was used. The adequate sample size of 345, using Freund and William's statistic formula. 258 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 75 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.78 which was also good. Data was presented and analysed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analysed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool.

Data Presentation

The Relationship between Training Workshops and Continues Development of SMEs in Enugu

Table 1: Responses on the relationship between training workshops and continues development of SMEs in Enugu

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	The employee undergoing training enhances their skills	445 89 34.5	280 70 27.1	36 12 4.7	30 30 11.6	57 57 22.1	848 258 100%	3.40	1.581	Agree
2	The knowledge of job is improved through conference and seminars	585 117 45.3	252 63 24.4	42 14 5.4	24 12 4.7	52 52 20.2	955 258 100%	3.70	1.558	Agree
3	The building of employee confidence in their abilities is done through development.	530 106 41.1	304 79 30.6	8 8 3.1	58 29 11.2	36 36 14.0	936 258 100%	3.74	1.444	Agree
4	Training sustains employees skill relevance	590 118 45.7	236 59 22.9	21 7 2.7	86 43 16.7	31 31 12.0	964 258 100%	3.74	1.474	Agree
5	Fewer accidents occurs with knowledge and skills.	530 106 41.1	292 73 28.3	45 15 5.8	50 25 9.7	39 39 15.1	953 258 100%	3.71	1.462	Agree
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.658	1.504	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1, 159 respondents out of 258 representing 61.6 percent agreed that the employee undergoing training enhances their skills with mean score 3.40 and standard deviation of 1.581. The knowledge of job is improved through conference and seminars 180 respondents representing 69.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.70 and standard deviation of 1.550. The building of employee confidence in their abilities are done through development 185 respondents representing 71.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.74 and standard deviation of 1.444. Training sustains employees skill relevance 177 respondents representing 68.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.74 and 1.474. Fewer accidents occur with knowledge and skills 179 respondents representing 69.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.71 and standard deviation 1.462.

The Relationship between Professional Support Network and Productivity of SMEs

Table 2: Responses on the relationship between professional support network and productivity of SMEs

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Building network is essential to forging long-term relationships	550 110 42.6	260 65 25.2	48 16 6.2	44 22 8.5	45 45 17.4	947 258 100%	3.67	1.516	Agree
2	The organisational reputation over time is established.	590 118 45.7	208 52 20.2	30 10 3.9	70 35 13.6	43 43 16.7	941 258 100%	3.65	1.557	Agree
3	Good Professional support networking has a basic of trust and support.	445 89 34.5	308 77 29.8	93 31 12.0	15 5 1.9	56 56 21.7	917 258 100%	3.53	1.513	Agree
4	Career growth and learning opportunities are maximized through professional networking.	555 111 43.0	308 77 29.8	42 14 5.4	80 40 15.5	16 16 6.2	1001 258 100%	3.88	1.286	Agree
5	There is strength of the organisational network business connections.	445 89 34.5	308 77 29.8	63 21 8.1	70 35 13.6	36 36 14.0	922 258 100%	3.57	1.432	Agree
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.66	1.4608	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 175 respondents out of 258 representing 67.8 percent agreed that Building network is essential to forging long-term relationships with mean score 3.67 and standard deviation of 1.516. The organizational reputation over time is established 170 respondents representing 65.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.557. Good Professional support networking has a basic of trust and support 166 respondents representing 64.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.53 and standard deviation of 1.513. Career growth and learning opportunities are maximized through professional networking 188 respondents representing 72.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.88 and standard deviation of 1.286. There is strength of the organizational network business connections 166 respondents representing 64.3 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.57 and standard deviation 1.432.

Test of Hypotheses

Training Workshops has Relationship with Continues Development of SMEs in Enugu.

Table 3, Shows Pearson correlation on training workshops has relationship with continues development of SMEs in Enugu.

		Correlations				
		The employee undergoing training enhances their skills	The knowledge of job is improved through conference and seminars	The building of employee confidence in their abilities are done through development.	Training sustains employees skill relevance	Fewer accidents occurs with knowledge and skills.
The employee undergoing training enhances their skills	Pearson Correlation	1	.578**	.534**	.757**	.508**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
The knowledge of job is improved through conference and seminars	Pearson Correlation	.578**	1	.574**	.535**	.663**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
The building of employee confidence in their abilities are done through development.	Pearson Correlation	.534**	.574**	1	.656**	.379**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
Training sustains employees skill relevance	Pearson Correlation	.757**	.535**	.656**	1	.480**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
Fewer accidents occurs with knowledge and skills.	Pearson Correlation	.508**	.663**	.379**	.480**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	258	258	258	258	258

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 is the Pearson correlation matrix on training workshops has relationship with continues development showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .379 < 757. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2 tailed) and implies that training workshops had positive significant relationship with continues development of SMEs in Enugu ($r=.379 < 757$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 879 degree of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r=.379 < 757, p>.05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed $r = .379 < 757$ is greater than the table value of .195, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude training workshops had positive significant relationship with continues development of SMEs in Enugu as reported in the probability value of ($r= .379 < 757, p>.05$).

Professional Support Network has Relationship with Productivity of SMEs

Table 4: Shows Pearson correlation on Professional support network has relationship with productivity of SMEs

		Correlations				
		Building network is essential to forging long-term relationships	The organizational reputation over time is established.	Good Professional support networking has a basic of trust and support.	Career growth and learning opportunities are maximized through professional networking.	There is strength of the organizational network business connections.
Building network is essential to forging long-term relationships	Pearson Correlation	1	.592**	.499**	.401**	.474**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
The organizational reputation over time is established.	Pearson Correlation	.592**	1	.467**	.422**	.456**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
Good Professional support networking has a basic of trust and support.	Pearson Correlation	.499**	.467**	1	.657**	.975**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
Career growth and learning opportunities are maximized through professional networking.	Pearson Correlation	.401**	.422**	.657**	1	.646**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	258	258	258	258	258
There is strength of the organizational network business connections.	Pearson Correlation	.474**	.456**	.975**	.646**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	258	258	258	258	258

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 is the Pearson correlation matrix on professional support network and productivity showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.401 < .975$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2 tailed) and implies that professional support network had positive significant relationship with productivity of SMEs ($r = .401 < .975$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 879 degree of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .401 < .975$, $p > .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed $r = .401 < .975$ is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude professional support network had positive significant relationship with productivity of SMEs as reported in the probability value of ($r = .401 < .975$, $p > .05$).

Discussions of Findings

Training Workshops had Positive Significant Relationship with Continues Development of SMEs in Enugu

The result of hypotheses one showed the computed $r = .379 < 757$ was greater than the table value of .000, we concluded training workshops had positive significant relationship with continues development of SMEs in Enugu as reported in the probability value of ($r = .379 < 757, p < .05$). In support of these hypotheses, Okonkwo, Onyeze and Ochiaka (2019) conducted a study on the Empowering the Uneducated Youths in Nigeria through Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria. The general aim of this research work is to examine “the ways of empowering the uneducated youths in Nigeria through Small and Medium Scale Enterprise. The findings includes that the roles of small and medium scale enterprises in youth empowerment in Enugu State are entrepreneurship promotion, provision of employment opportunities, mobilization of savings and financial resources for productive enterprise activities and equitable growth across regions and between men and women, the contributions of government in SME development are provision of infrastructural development, promotion of small and medium scale enterprises through its policies, provision of capital and loans to small and medium scale business owners and provision of skill acquisition centres in diverse areas. In conclusion, capital formation has affected the role of small and medium scale enterprises in youth empowerment in Enugu State to a very great extent, the challenges militating against the efforts of small and medium scale enterprises in youth empowerment in Enugu State are financial problems, management problems, infrastructure problems and sociocultural problems.

Professional Support Network had Positive Significant Relationship with Productivity of SMEs

The findings of hypotheses two reveals that the computed $r = .401 < 975$ was greater than the table value of .000, we concluded professional support network had positive significant relationship with productivity of SMEs as reported in the probability value of ($r = .401 < 975, p < .05$). In the study of Fatai, et al. (2018) on the Nexus Between Informal Networks and Risk-Taking: Implications for Improving the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. An evolving dimension of entrepreneurial research reveals that entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial networks are critical factors in fostering performance outcomes. The results revealed that both risk-taking and informal networks have significant positive effect on SMEs performance. It is recommended that SMEs managers should strive to embrace risk-taking as well as optimize the opportunities offered by informal networks potential towards expanding their contacts and enhance SMEs performance. The study contributes to entrepreneurial orientation dimension and informal institutional framework through the integration of risk- taking and informal networks with SMEs performance.

Conclusion

The study concluded that training workshops and professional support network had positive significant relationship with competences development and productivity of SMEs. Entrepreneurship education cultivates innovative talents, which are an important driving force for future development. Entrepreneurial characteristics which include risk taking propensity, innovativeness and self-confidence are predictors of SME performance. The roles of entrepreneurs are important because of their contribution to the economic growth for both developed and developing countries. Factors influence the success of SMEs is very important to know because it is the low level of business success.

Recommendations

- i. Entrepreneurship tutors, teachers, lecturers or trainers should also be trained in other to ensure their competence in impacting the knowledge to others. Also, they should ensure that students practice the theoretical aspect of what has been taught if the need arises.
- ii. In terms of recruitment, the managers of SMEs are advised to not only look at academic qualification but they should also consider competency as it would help to boost organizational performance and productivity.

References

- Aladejebi, O. (2020). The Impact of Entrepreneurial Networks on The Performance of Small Business in Nigeria. *Archives of Business Research*, 8(3), 281-293.
- Alkahtani, A., Nordin, N., & Rizwan, K. (2020). Government support enhances the relation between networking structure and sustainable competitive performance among SMEs. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-020-00127-3>
- Barinua, V., & Okoro, M. C. (2022). Entrepreneurial Characteristics and Business Performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in Enugu State. *International Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Research*, 13(3), 2360-989X.
- Cambridge. (2023). Networking skills. <https://www.ibs.cam.ac.uk/entrepreneurship/resources/networking-skills/>
- Cosmin, O., Gheorghe, N., & Raluca, C. (2012). The concept of performance in business organizations – Case study on the employee performance in Romanian business organizations. *Proceedings of the 6th International Management Conference. "Approaches in Organisational Management,"* 15-16 November 2012, Bucharest, Romania, 1-7.
- Criniti, A. M. (2021). Components of an Entrepreneur. <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/362629>
- Ede, T. E., & Mbah, P. C. (2020). What is the Nexus between organizational compensation and Employee Performance? *Thomson Reuters indexed journal, Solid State Technology*, 63(5), 6593 – 6604.
- Egele, A. C., Muhammad, K., & Mutenyo, J. (2018). Entrepreneurial personal networks and performance of small and medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Kano State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research*, 5(17), 2348-6848.
- Elnaga, A., & Imran, A. (2013). The Effect of Training on Employee Performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(4), 2222-2839.
- Emezue, L. N., & Onwujekwe, U. G. (2020). Effect of entrepreneurship education on performance of small and medium scale enterprise in Enugu state. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 8(5), 33-51.
- Eze, F. O., Agbo, M., & Mbah, P. C. (2022). Effect of E-management practices on the performance of shopping mall in Enugu State. *Advance Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Development*, 6(5), 38-45.
- Fatai, A. L., Omotayo, A. A., Oluwole, O. I., Omisade, E. A., & Akeem, A. T. (2018). Nexus Between Informal Networks and Risk-Taking: Implications for Improving the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 17(2), 1939-6104.
- Habiyaremye, P., Ayebele, D., & Wanyama, B. S. (2017). Job-Rotation, Utilization of Workshops, and Performance of SMEs: An Empirical Study from the Gasabo District in Rwanda. In *Management Challenges in Different Types of African Firms*. DOI:10.1007/978-981-10-4536-3_11.
- Hasan, S. M., Khan, E. A., & Nabi, M. N. U. (2017). Entrepreneurial education at the university level and entrepreneurship development. *Education and Training*, 59(7/8), 888–906.
- Hisrich, R. D., Peters, M. P., & Shepherd, D. A. (2017). *Entrepreneurship*. MC Graw Hills. ISBN 978-0-07-811284-3.
- Indeed Editorial Team (2022). What Is Professional Networking? (Learn and Master It). <https://uk.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/professional-networking>
- Indeed. (2023). Developing competence: definition, types and how-to guide. <https://uk.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/developing-competence>.
- Johanns, A. M. (2021). Understanding profitability. Retrieved from <https://www.extension.iastate.edu/agdm/wholefarm/html/c3-24.html>
- King, E. (2011). Education is fundamental to development and growth. Retrieved from <https://blogs.worldbank.org/education/education-is-fundamental-to-development-and-growth>.

Koa, D., & Stevenson, H. (2020). Entrepreneurship development in South Africa [Internet]. 1984. Available from: <http://www.google.com/search> [Accessed: 2020-07-04].

Kulo, V. A., Agbogo, R. A., & Okudare, J. U. (2017). Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Business EDUCATION (NIGJBED)*, 4(1), 50-56.

Lucid. (2023). What is a Workshop? <https://www.lucidmeetings.com/glossary/workshop>.

Mahmood, R., Zahari, A. S. M., Ibrahim, N., Jaafar, N. F. H. N., & Yaacob, N. M. (2021). The impact of Entrepreneur Education on Business performance. *Asian journal of University Education (AJUE)*, 16(4), 171-180.

Mango (2023). What is Training? <https://www.mangolive.com/what-is-training>.

Mario, F., Haase, H., & Pereira, A. (2016). Empirical Study about the Role of Social Networks in SME Performance. *Journal of Systems and Information Technology*, (4). DOI:10.1108/JSIT-06-2016-0036.

Mbah, P. C., Aga, C. C., & Onyia, E. (2018). Effect of Human Capital Development in Organizational Performance in Manufacturing Industries in South-East Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 7(3), 60–78.

McNamara, C. (2018). Performance management: what is "performance"? (Performance Defined). Retrieved from <https://managementhelp.org/perfo>

Nwekeaku, C. (2013). Entrepreneurship education and challenges to Nigerian universities. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(3), 51.

Okoli, I. E. N., & Agugwu, C. C. (2022). Uncovering the Relationship between Entrepreneurship Training on Business Growth among SMEs in Southeast Nigeria. *European Journal of Business & Management Research*, 7(1), 2507-1076.

Okonkwo, P. C., Onyeze, C. N., & Ochiaka, D. I. (2019). Empowering the Uneducated Youths in Nigeria through Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 4(10), 2415-6671.

Oluka, S. N., & Nwafor, B. C. (2022). Entrepreneurial Competencies: A Sine Qua Non for the Successful Operation of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) by Graduates of Technology and Vocational Education from Tertiary Institutions in Enugu State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Research Review*, 1(1), 77-87.

Omolo, J. W. (2015). Training and Development on Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kisumu County, Kenya. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 2(8), 2394-5931.

Potters, C. (2021). The difference between profitability and profit. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/012715/what-difference-between-profitability-and-profit.asp>

Ukwuani, B. O., Mbah, P. C., & Ugochukwu, L. N. (2018). Entrepreneurship and Organizational Growth of Hapel Manufacturing Company. *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(8), 993-1000.

Vaishali, D. (2021). Components of Entrepreneurship. <https://dutchuncles.in/aspire/entrepreneurship-key-components-and-entrepreneurial-mindset/>

Victoria L. (2018). Building a Professional Support Network. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/building-professional-support-network-victoria-lynden>.

Wei, X., Liu, X., & Sha, J. (2019). How Does the Entrepreneurship Education Influence the Students' Innovation? Testing on the Multiple Mediation Model. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01557/full>

Zahid, S., Khan, M. A., Zhen, Y., Adnan, K., Muhammad, H., & Aaqub, S. (2021). An Investigation of Entrepreneurial SMEs' Network Capability and Social Capital to Accomplish Innovativeness: A Dynamic Capability Perspective. DOI: 10.1177/21582440211036089.

Zavvy (2023). 8-Step Competence Development for Competitive Businesses (With Process & Tool). <https://www.zavvy.io/blog/competence-development>.